

DEVELOPING SPEAKING CONFIDENCE OF ESL LEARNERS

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Annotation. *This thesis examines the development of oral confidence in learners of English as a second language. In addition, this thesis examines the problem of developing confidence in oral speech. Confidence is an important factor that influences students' communication skills, fluency, and class participation. Many students experience fear of making mistakes, anxiety about speaking, and low self-esteem, which hinder oral communication. This thesis analyzes the theoretical aspects of oral confidence and the emotional factors that affect learning, and suggests effective communication strategies such as pair work, group work, role-playing, and interactive activities. Finally, it suggests that building confidence can help reduce anxiety and improve oral communication.*

Key words: confidence, fluency, anxiety, motivation, participation, interaction.

Аннотация. *В тезисе рассматривается развитие уверенности в устной речи у изучающих английский язык как второй. Кроме того, в работе исследуется проблема развития уверенности в устной речи. Уверенность является важным фактором, влияющим на коммуникативные навыки студентов, беглость речи и их участие в занятиях. Многие студенты испытывают страх совершить ошибки, тревогу перед публичными выступлениями и низкую самооценку, что препятствует устной коммуникации. В этом тезисе анализируются теоретические аспекты уверенности в устной речи и эмоциональные факторы, влияющие на обучение, а также предлагаются эффективные стратегии коммуникации, такие как работа в парах, работа в группах, ролевые игры и интерактивные занятия. Наконец, предполагается, что развитие уверенности может помочь снизить тревожность и улучшить устную коммуникацию.*

Ключевые слова: уверенность, беглость, тревожность, мотивация, участие, взаимодействие.

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tezisdagi ingliz tilini ikkinchi til sifatida o'rganuvchilarda og'zaki ishonchning rivojlanishini o'rgatadi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu tezisdagi og'zaki nutqda ishonchni rivojlantirish muammosi ko'rib chiqiladi. Ishonch talabalarning muloqot qobiliyatlari, ravonligi va darsda ishtirok etishiga ta'sir qiluvchi muhim omil hisoblanadi. Ko'pgina talabalar xato qilishdan qo'rqish, gapirishdan xavotirlanish va o'ziga past baho berishni boshdan kechirishadi, bu esa og'zaki muloqotga xalaqit beradi. Ushbu tezisdagi og'zaki ishonchning nazariy jihatlarini va o'rganishga ta'sir qiluvchi hissiy omillarni tahlil qiladi va juftlik ishi, guruh ishi, rol o'ynash va interaktiv mashg'ulotlar kabi samarali muloqot strategiyalarini taklif qiladi. Va nihoyat, unda ishonchni shakllantirish xavotirni kamaytirish va og'zaki muloqotni yaxshilashga yordam berishi mumkinligi ta'kidlangan.*

Kalit so'zlar: ishonch, ravonlik, xavotir, motivatsiya, ishtirok, o'zaro ta'sir.

Introduction. In recent years, the development of oral fluency has become a major goal in teaching English as a second language. Many students, despite having a good understanding of grammar, hesitate to speak due to fear of making mistakes, anxiety, and lack of confidence.

As Krashen has pointed out: “Emotional barriers such as anxiety and lack of confidence can hinder language acquisition even when students have access to understandable information”. [1;30-31]

Speaking confidence in the language learning process is the psychological readiness to speak without fear of making mistakes, which is a key factor in quickly achieving fluency. As Azimova wrote in her article: “Speaking is the ability to use a particular language”. [2;609]

Psychological factors play a significant role in the development of speaking confidence among learners of English as a second language (ESL). According to Akhmedova’s statement, “Searches of anxiety have various types: fear of making a mistake, a feeling of constant evaluation by the teacher or fellow students, and besides vocabulary limitation” [3;430]

Fear of making mistakes makes them hesitate, fearing judgment or embarrassment. If teachers correct mistakes too often or focus only on accuracy, anxiety in the classroom can increase. According to Krashen, high anxiety can hinder language learning by increasing the emotional filter. [1;30-31]

Low self-esteem also reduces self-confidence. Students who underestimate their abilities speak less, while positive feedback and encouragement help them feel more comfortable and actively participate in class. Therefore, teachers need to create a caring and safe environment and use strategies that reduce anxiety and increase students' confidence in speaking.

<https://share.google/ltVbjXWhcYsHG6naT>

Practical strategies help students learning English as a second language gain confidence in speaking while creating an interactive and supportive classroom environment. First of all, we should pay attention to confidence. The reason of this is, if you have a lot of knowledge but lack confidence and if you lack confidence in speaking, you can not help but feel overwhelmed when speaking to others, because you will forget all the knowledge you have acquired and begin speaking insecurely and incorrectly. This is a major drawback for many students of any language, such as English.

However, there are several solutions to these issues. Let us examine these solutions, before getting for one decision. Firstly, a supportive and interactive classroom environment allows students to practice English without fear of making mistakes. Secondly, using specific techniques reduces anxiety, increases activity and gradually improves verbal fluency.

An effective method is working in pairs and groups, where students discuss topics in small groups or with a partner. Harmer argues that, “Collaborative work encourages students to express themselves more freely and communicate naturally”. [4;72-75] Role-playing is also useful because it allow students to act out real-life situations. According to Brown, role-playing

helps students take risks in a safe environment and overcome the fear of making mistakes. [5;189-192]

Furthermore, have several advises to future learners to improve confidence in speech:

№	Advice	Why it works?
1	Pair and group work	Less intimidating, more speaking opportunities.
2	Interactive games and tasks	Makes learning enjoyable and motivates participation.
3	Daily speaking practice	Builds fluency and habit.
4	Positive feedback and encouragement	Reduces anxiety, boosts motivation.
5	Developing integral confidence	Positive self-talk strengthens motivation.

By the way, Teachers should encourage and praise students, not just correct their mistakes. In a safe and supportive classroom environment, students will express themselves more confidently and gradually gain self-confidence. Regular practice will help them become more engaged in the learning process and improve their English.

Conclusion. In overall, Developing confidence in speaking is crucial for successfully learning English as a second language. By overcoming psychological barriers and applying practical strategies, teachers can create a supportive environment that encourages students to express themselves freely and actively participate in discussions. In this way, students gradually improve their fluency, self-confidence, and overall communication skills. I strongly believe that, through these ways, namely through strategies we will solve these troubles and will improve our confidence in the future life.

REFERENCE

1. Krashen, S. D. (1985). The Input Hypothesis: Issues and Implications. Longman. P.30-31;
2. Азимова М.И. (2021). УВЕРЕННОСТЬ В УСТНОЙ РЕЧИ ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА. Экономика и социум, (5-1 (84)), 609-612;
3. Akhmedova С. . (2025). ПСИХОЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ТРЕВОЖНОСТИ В ПРОЦЕССЕ УСТНОГО ОБЩЕНИЯ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. Interpretation and Researches, (9(55-2). Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/international-scientific/article/view/101169>. P.430;
4. Harmer, J. (2007). The Practice of English Language Teaching (4th ed.). Pearson Longman. P.72-75;
5. Brown, H. D. (2001). Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy (2nd ed.). Pearson Education. P. 189-192;
6. Mirusmonova Ziyoda Ziyodullo qizi, & Ergasheva Mukaddas Toshtemirovna. (2025). THE ROLE OF REFLECTIVE TEACHING IN IMPROVING ESL LESSONS. Towards a new economy, pedagogy and technology, 1(4), 108–115. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17767505>